

Towards Turbulence-Free Education: A Comprehensive Analysis of Vision and Mission Statements in Turkish Aviation Education Institutions

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Article Info	Abstract
REVIEW ARTICLE	<p>This study undertakes a comprehensive analysis of the mission and vision statements of Turkish academic units conferring bachelor's degrees in aviation, offering insights into the foundational policies shaping the nation's aviation education sector. Investigating 16 academic units from diverse universities, the research reveals a strong commitment to education and training, scientific studies, and flexibility in programs, emphasizing a dedication to producing a highly skilled aviation workforce. Notably, the mission statements consistently echo themes of global competitiveness, ethical values, social responsibility, and an unwavering commitment to excellence, positioning these institutions as crucial contributors to the dynamic aviation and space sciences landscape. From a visionary perspective, the academic units aspire to global recognition, leading positions in aviation education, and active roles in national and regional development. The emphasis on scientific excellence, innovation, and international collaboration points to a future where graduates are envisioned as visionary leaders and contributors to the evolving aviation industry. As Türkiye progresses in the aviation education sector, this research provides valuable insights for academic institutions, policymakers, and industry stakeholders</p>
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1. Introduction

Aviation is one of the most critical and essential sectors in the modern world due to its contribution to the global economy and community. Its contributions to the contemporary world include but are not limited to economic development (Aktemur, 2021), environmental sustainability (Singh et al., 2018; Yakovlieva et al., 2021), climate change awareness (Singh et al. 2018), socio-economic development (Sultana, 2020), connectivity and accessibility (Reader et al., 2006), disaster relief and humanitarian aids (Dobie et al., 2018; Ertem et al., 2017), technological advancement, and national/international security. Because of these inputs, it is not surprising to see the attention the industry attracts from governments, regional authorities, global businesses, and researchers worldwide.

Considering the information mentioned earlier, it is crucial for governments and relevant authorities to formulate policies that not only support the aviation industry but also prioritize the development of a highly skilled workforce. Personnel working in the aviation industry play a vital role in its success and growth. As a rapidly developing and dynamic sector, the aviation industry relies on qualified and skilled professionals who possess technical expertise, adhere to safety protocols, and are proficient in handling advanced technologies.

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Michel and his friends (2007) emphasize the significance of the human factor in aviation, stating that even the most sophisticated and expensive devices hold no value in the hands of individuals who lack the necessary knowledge and training. This statement highlights the indispensable role of education and training in paving the way for sustainable development within the aviation industry.

To ensure a well-qualified human workforce, individuals seeking to work in the field should have access to an environment that enables them to receive both theoretical and practical education and training (Karaağaoğlu, 2015). Therefore, it is imperative for authorities to establish a well-organized education system, with qualified higher education institutions being a key component. Academic institutions offering aviation education begin at high school level and continue through higher education. These institutions are responsible for producing the skilled workforce that drives sustainable development in the aviation industry. As such, the number of these institutions has grown in tandem with the sector's development, providing the necessary training for the workforce over the years. Industry-university cooperation is essential for the healthy and sustainable development of aviation (Yalçınkaya, 2014).

2. Theoretical Background

In Türkiye, where the significance of education in achieving success is highly emphasized, higher education in aviation dates back to the 1940s. To begin, the first aviation education in a university in the country was provided by Istanbul Technical University. The university provided the first aviation education under the Mechanical Engineering Department major in 1941. The establishment of this development was pioneered by Nuri Demirağ, who was a pioneer in breaking new ground in Turkish civil aviation (Bilkay, 2021). Subsequently, Anadolu University and Turkish Aeronautical Association University were the other two universities to step into the era of aviation. Today, what is now known as the Faculty of Aviation and Space Sciences at Eskişehir Technical University was established in 1986 as the Anadolu University Vocational School of Civil Aviation (Anadolu Üniversitesi, 2023).

Similarly, Turkish Aeronautical Association University started its activities as the first aviation university in Türkiye and the 37th in the world. Specifically, the university was founded in 1925 on the accumulated knowledge of the Turkish Aeronautical Association, which was established on the instructions of Atatürk, the founder of the Republic of Türkiye (Türk Hava Kurumu Üniversitesi, 2023). The establishment of these academic units, representing the country's first attempts, has been a source of inspiration for Türkiye's future academy in the field of aviation. In today's Türkiye, 32 academic units actively provide bachelor's degrees in the field of aviation (Öğrenci Seçme ve Yerleştirme Merkezi, 2023). As the industry thrives, the demand for skilled personnel also rises. However, the key word at this point is the degree of qualification the graduates from those academic units have. In the sense of personnel planning, the companies in an industry plan not only the numbers but also the qualifications. Strategic planning plays a crucial role for both businesses and educational institutions. Extensive studies demonstrated the importance of strategic planning for the quality of education (Albon et al., 2016; Machado et al., 2004) Accordingly, it is unsurprising to see strategic planning being widely used in the Turkish higher education system as part of a strategic management approach. Vision and mission statements are two primary components of strategic planning. Moreover, to execute strategic planning successfully, it is necessary to formulate an organization's vision and mission statement correctly (Ozdem, 2011). Therefore, it is important for educational institutions to have a well-structured vision and mission statements to have a sustainable success in the era of the related topic.

A mission statement articulates the core purpose and fundamental reasons for an organization's existence. It is formalized to define the unique and enduring purpose of an organization. Key questions a well-defined mission statement seeks to address include "What is our fundamental objective?", "What do we stand for as an institution?", and "What do we seek to accomplish?". In addition to conveying purpose, mission statements outline organizations' operating boundaries, operational activities, responsibilities, and business philosophies (Erol & Kanbur, 2014). On the other hand, a vision statement defines a point that an organization seeks to reach. In other words, a vision statement portrays a conceptual picture of an organization of the future (Altinkurt & Yılmaz, 2011; Emini & Ayaz, 2020).

Mission and vision statements are significant for organizations. Both demonstrate the quality of strategic planning and strategic management. These statements provide essential information about the organization's image and activities to stakeholders. In addition, mission and vision statements guide the organization's employees and provide perspectives on management and leadership concepts for its executives (Kubilay,

2023). In addition, these statements serve as guiding principles that shape these academic units' strategic direction and decision-making processes, as well. Although mission and vision concepts are two essential elements of strategic planning, organizations have been observed not to give enough attention to these concepts and to randomly determine texts with a populist approach (Muslu, 2014).

Understanding the importance of the vision and mission statements, a considerable number of researchers paid attention to the topic. A certain number of content analysis studies have been conducted on the vision and mission statements of varying higher education institutions in Türkiye (Emini & Ayaz, 2020; Ocak & Karabulut, 2017; S. Özdemir & Karadağ, 2015; Yavuz & Ormankıran, 2020).

In one of those studies, tourism in higher education was the focus. Ormankıran (2020) conducted a study to identify distinctive and common elements in the mission and vision statements of faculties/schools providing undergraduate tourism education in both state and private universities. The research analyzed 52 institutions, including 41 tourism faculties and 11 tourism schools. Using the qualitative research method of document analysis, Ormankıran aimed to describe the expressions found in the mission and vision statements of tourism faculties and schools. The findings of the study revealed a frequent emphasis on integrating vocational education with tourism and transforming theoretical knowledge into practical application. According to the author, a significant alignment was observed among the mission and vision statements identified within the strategic plans of these institutions.

Another related study was conducted by Emini and Ayaz (2020). The authors conducted their study on the mission and vision statements of universities in the Marmara Region, with a specific focus on faculties related to Economic and Administrative Sciences, Political Sciences, Social Sciences, and Management Sciences. The aim of their research was to explore how universities contribute to and navigate ongoing processes of change and transformation in a rapidly evolving world. The research highlighted the importance of effective mission and vision statements in directing institutional resources towards innovation, which is a crucial aspect in today's higher education landscape. The study reveals distinct patterns in the usage of innovative concepts within the statements. State universities prioritize innovation in academic and problem-solving domains, while private universities prioritize innovation in student development. Notable similarities and differences in the context of innovation between state and private universities suggest varying strategic priorities. The study highlights potential challenges in unique vision formulation by identifying instances of identical vision statements between faculties in the Marmara Region and those in other regions. The findings shed light on the differing practices in articulating mission and vision statements and provide insights into the strategic priorities related to innovation in both state and foundation universities within the Marmara Region. The researchers claimed that their offered valuable insights into how universities strategically position themselves to foster innovation.

Another study was conducted by Öcal (2023). The researcher conducted a content analysis of the mission and vision statements of 19 public universities in Türkiye with Recreation Departments, at macro (university), meso (faculty), and micro (department) levels. The aim was to reveal the expected graduate qualifications of recreation experts. The study found that universities, faculties, and departments primarily focused on increasing students' professional knowledge. Additionally, faculties emphasized social values such as patriotism, while graduate skills such as communication, teamwork, organizational behavior, and experience were given less emphasis. Recreation departments aimed to prioritize leadership and supervisor/manager qualities for their graduates, as well as increasing their professional knowledge. The author reported an inconsistency in expected graduate qualifications between university, faculty, and department levels. He also added that the qualifications that can be gained through internships or work experience were systematically ignored. In his study, author claimed that the inconsistencies and deficiencies would create negative effects on employability of graduates and as well as corporate images of organizations.

While there is a wealth of research on mission and vision statements in various higher education institutions, there is a lack of specific academic studies on higher education institutions affiliated with aviation. This study aims to conduct a content analysis on the vision and mission statements of the faculties/schools in Türkiye which provide bachelor's degrees in aviation. It is believed that the study will fill a significant gap in the field of aviation education matters and make a valuable contribution to the existing literature.

By addressing this topic, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the vision and mission statement of aviation education institutions in Türkiye and offer insights. The study plans to identify recurring themes, key priorities, and the overarching vision articulated in these statements. Additionally, the analysis aims to uncover the shared values and priorities guiding Türkiye's aviation educational endeavors.

3. Methodology

This study utilizes content analysis, a qualitative research method. In qualitative methods, researchers focus on the knowledge embedded in the data collected. The process mostly starts with sampling and continues with the data collection phase. The data that can be analyzed under qualitative research methods mainly include written sources, detailed descriptions of observed behaviors, visual data objects, and artifacts of the research subject (Emini & Ayaz, 2020; M. Özdemir, 2010). Since the subjected data in this study is written sources, a content analysis should be considered as the appropriate method to be utilized.

The universe of the study consisted of all faculties/schools in Türkiye which provide bachelor's degrees in aviation. A total of 32 faculties/schools were included in the study. To identify faculties/schools that offer bachelor's degrees in aviation, the statistics published online by the Student Selection and Placement Center (ÖSYM) were examined. Based on the data obtained from "the table of undergraduate programs in higher education that admitted students in 2023", the names of 32 academic units were finally identified.

To ensure validity and reliability, using only English official webpages of target faculties/schools as data sources was decided. Therefore, it was possible to avoid confusion in the translation process and to reach data online by the readers. After an extensive online search, only the vision and mission statements of 16 academic units were collected. The rest of the schools either did not have their websites in English or did not mention their mission or vision statements in English. As a result, the vision and mission statements of 16 faculties/schools as the study sample were available to be examined. The exclusion of certain institutions without English content was explicitly addressed, emphasizing the need for a standardized approach.

The primary aim of this study is to conduct an in-depth analysis of the vision and mission statements of faculties/schools in Türkiye offering bachelor's degrees in aviation. The findings are not intended for broad generalization, but rather to provide a detailed understanding of linguistic and thematic trends within this specific context.

4. Results and Discussion

Prior to commencing the analysis, it is imperative to provide an overview of the universities under study. Table 1 provides specific information on the names, the ownership, and finally the statements' availability of the academic units. As it shown in Table 1, the study includes 32 academic units from 30 different universities. However, only 16 of the 32 academic units have their mission and vision statements available in English. These 16 academic units comprise of 5 private and 11 state institutions.

Table 1: The List of Higher Education Institutions Offering Bachelor's Degrees In Aviation

The Name of The Academic Unit	Mission& Vision Statements
Adana Alparslan Türkeş Science and Technology University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	NA
Alanya Alaattin Keykubat University (Antalya) - Gazipaşa Faculty of Aviation and Space Sciences (State)	A
Ankara Yıldırım Beyazıt University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	NA
Antalya Bilim University - Civil Aviation Vocational School (Private)	NA
Atilım University (Ankara) - School of Civil Aviation (Private)	A
Balıkesir University - School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Beykoz University (İstanbul) - School of Civil Aviation (Private)	A
Dicle University (Diyarbakır) - School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Erciyes University (Kayseri) - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	A
Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University – Ali Cavit Celebioğlu School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Eskişehir Technical University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	A
Fırat University - School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Gaziantep University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	A
Gebze Technical University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	NA
Hasan Kalyoncu University (Gaziantep) - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (Private)	A
İskenderun Technical University (Hatay) - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	NA
İstanbul Nişantaşı University - School of Civil Aviation (Private)	NA
İstanbul Technical University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	A
Kastamonu University - School of Civil Aviation (State)	A

Kocaeli Univesity - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	NA
Malatya Turgut Özel University - School of Civil Aviation (State)	A
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University – Dalaman School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Necmettin Erbakan University - School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Özyeğin University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (Private)	A
Samsun University – Özdemir Bayraktar Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	A
Samsun University - School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Selçuk University (Konya) - School of Civil Aviation (State)	A
Sivas Science and Technology University - Faculty of Aviation and Space Sciences (State)	A
Suleyman Demirel University (Isparta) - School of Civil Aviation (State)	NA
Tarsus University - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (State)	A
University of Turkish Aeronautical Association - Faculty of Air Transportation (Private)	A
University of Turkish Aeronautical Association - Faculty of Aeronautics and Astronautics (Private)	NA

Source: *Öğrenci Seçme ve Yerleştirme (2023).*

To conduct the analysis, first, the language used in these statements was analyzed to understand the mission statements of the academic university. The analysis revealed common patterns and consistencies in certain phrases used in the mission statements of the subjected academic units. As shown in Table 2, the statements include education and training, flexibility and interdisciplinary approaches, scientific studies, global competitiveness, ethical values and social responsibility, entrepreneurship and innovation, national and regional development contribution, and commitment to excellence.

Table 2: Frequency of Mission Statements

Themes	State	Private	Total
Education and training	10	4	14
Flexibility and interdisciplinary approaches	6	1	7
Scientific studies	9	5	14
Global competitiveness	7	3	10
Ethical values and social responsibility	11	4	15
Entrepreneurship and innovation	8	3	11
National and regional development contribution	8	3	11
Commitment to excellence	7	4	11

Source: *Composed by the author*

As previously stated, a mission statement should relate to core purposes. Therefore, it is highly expected that an academic unit's mission statement includes the words 'education and training'. Upon reviewing mission statements of academic units, there is a unanimous emphasis on providing high-quality education and practical training. This ensures that graduates are well-equipped with the theoretical knowledge and skills demanded by the aviation industry. Therefore, it can be concluded that aviation-related academic units are similar to other educational institutions in terms of including education and training in their mission statement (Ozdem, 2011; S. Özdemir & Karadağ, 2015; Yavuz & Ormankıran, 2020).

“Scientific studies” is another frequently used expression in the mission statements of subjected academic units. The commitment to engaging in scientific studies is a recurrent expression, emphasizing the importance of research and academic advancement. Since the sample consists of academic units providing bachelor's degrees, it was likely to see “scientific studies” as part of mission statements. In summary, the pervasive use of the expression “scientific studies” within the mission statements of these academic units affirms the institutions' steadfast commitment to research and educational advancement. As these statements underscore, pursuing scientific studies is integral to the core mission of these academic units offering bachelor's degree programs in aviation. This commitment reflects a dedication to fostering an environment of intellectual curiosity and inquiry. It positions these institutions as pivotal contributors to the ongoing evolution of knowledge within the dynamic aviation field. In the context of bachelor's degree programs, this emphasis on scientific studies serves as a foundation for cultivating a new generation of professionals equipped with the critical thinking skills and research acumen necessary to navigate the complexities of the aviation landscape. As the institutions follow the statement, the future of aviation personnel in Türkiye will be likely to contribute to the sector more in a scientific matter.

Another expression considered education-related in the analysis is “Flexibility and Interdisciplinary Approaches”. Academic units often express a commitment to flexibility in their programs and interdisciplinary approaches to education. As the educational programs in the field of aviation are highly interdisciplinary, it is crucial to have flexibility in their strategic plans to adapt to the changes in the area. Studies supporting the importance of having a multidisciplinary approach in the field of aviation from different countries show that Turkish academic units providing aviation education follow the trends of their international counterparts (Beaufore, 2016; Gero, 2013; Zgodavová et al., 2019).

Although the expressions explained above are commonly used in educational institutions, it is also expected that the analysis includes field-related phrases. For instance, one of the expressions found in the mission statements is 'global competitiveness.' The mission statements consistently express a commitment to global competitiveness through scientific excellence and innovation in aviation and space sciences. Many mission statements in the research sample emphasize the need to equip graduates for success on a global scale. Given that the business industry is one of the most international sectors, educational institutions must prepare future personnel to compete with their international counterparts.

In conclusion, the recurrent use of expressions such as “global competitiveness” and the commitment to preparing graduates for success on an international scale underscores the overarching vision of these higher education institutions in aviation in aligning their educational objectives with the demands of the global aviation and space sciences landscape. This emphasis on global standards and excellence reflects the institutions' dedication to scientific innovation and resonates with the strategic priorities outlined by influential entities in the Turkish aviation sector.

The academic units of the study have a recurring theme of focusing on 'Ethical values and social responsibility' in their mission studies. This dedication involves teaching moral principles to students, encouraging social responsibility, and producing graduates who are not only technically skilled but also socially and environmentally aware. The integration of ethical values and social responsibility into education is consistently mentioned across the mission statements of the study sample. Phillips (2006) highlights the benefits of social responsibility, including cost-effective enhancement of competitive positioning, resource-efficient environmental stewardship, improvement of social conditions leading to favorable business locations, attraction of investors, and personal benefits for professionals engaged in charitable volunteer work. This analysis confirms the awareness of Turkish universities on the matter. The institutions under study recognize the importance of teaching ethical values and social responsibilities to future aviators. The publication of fifteen scholarly articles on 'ethics in aviation' in the last five years demonstrates the global significance of ethics in the aviation industry.

As shown in Table 2, the mission statements of subjected academic units frequently emphasize their commitment to excellence. This dedication is reflected in their aspirations for high standards in education, research, and industry engagement. In education, a commitment to excellence means delivering programs that exceed conventional standards. This includes developing rigorous curricula, using innovative teaching methods, and creating an environment that encourages intellectual curiosity and critical thinking among students. These academic units aim to produce graduates who meet and exceed the expectations of the aviation industry. The commitment to excellence in the statements also extends to research, with academic units aspiring to conduct cutting-edge studies that contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge in aviation and space sciences. This commitment involves promoting a research culture that encourages exploration, innovation, and the pursuit of solutions to the complex challenges facing the aviation sector. The institutions aim to position themselves at the forefront of academic inquiry through excellence in research, thereby enhancing their influence on national and international developments in the field. Furthermore, academic units prioritize establishing strong collaborations with industry stakeholders to demonstrate their commitment to excellence. This active engagement with the aviation sector allows them to shape its trajectory. The aim is to produce graduates with skills and knowledge that align with industry demands, foster partnerships that facilitate knowledge exchange, and contribute to advancements within the aviation industry. In the aviation industry, precision, safety, and technological innovation are paramount, making the commitment to excellence of utmost importance. Ensuring safety is crucial for aviation professionals and the industry. Therefore, the recurrent theme of 'Commitment to Excellence' in the mission statements of academic units highlights a collective dedication to elevating standards, fostering continuous improvement, and contributing to the field of aviation.

The mission statements consistently promote entrepreneurship and innovation in the field of aviation. They encourage research, interdisciplinary studies, and the development of new approaches to aeronautics and aerospace engineering. Phrases related to fostering entrepreneurship and innovation within the aviation sector are commonly found, especially in the mission statements of private universities. The significance of innovation in the aviation industry, which employs cutting-edge technology, is undeniable. The inclusion of innovation in the mission statements of the sample indicates the aviation educational institutions' keen interest in the matter. Encouraging students to be innovative is expected to yield positive results in the future, with the Turkish aviation industry expanding through innovative solutions to contemporary challenges.

The commitment to contributing to the economic and scientific development of Türkiye, both at the national and regional levels, is another recurring theme. Many of the mission statements in the study highlight a dedication to contributing to national and regional development, both economically and scientifically, aligning their goals with Türkiye's broader development plans. It is a well-established fact that aviation organizations contribute significantly to the socio-economic landscape of the regions in which they operate. It was expected that Turkish universities offering education in the field of aviation would be aware of this distinctive aspect of aviation and integrate this reality into their organizational policies. Investments in aviation contribute both economically and socially to the regions in which they operate. The analysis results indicate that future aviators are being educated to sustain and enhance this contribution to their environment (Macit & Duran, 2023).

The second part of the paper provides insights into the vision statements of the academic units subjected to the study. Since the definition of a vision statement differentiate from a mission statement, it will likely have a different theme focus. On the other hand, since the organizations originated in the field of aviation from an educational standpoint, there is a possibility of having certain similarities specific to the aviation industry in the statements.

When the analysis was conducted, the most common themes stood out are as shown in Table 3: global recognition and contribution, leading position in aviation education, contribution to national and regional development, scientific excellence and research development, quality education and training, international collaboration, and cooperation; and finally, innovation and original contribution to the field. As mentioned earlier, some themes, like the mission statement focusing on innovation, international collaboration, and cooperation, contributed to national and regional developments.

Table 3: Frequency of Vision Statements

Themes	State	Private	Total
Global recognition and contribution	4	4	8
Leading position in aviation, education	4	4	8
Contribution to national and regional development	4	4	8
Scientific excellence and research development	4	3	7
High quality education and training	3	4	7
International collaboration, and corporation	3	4	7
Innovation and original contribution to the field	3	3	6

Source: Composed by the author

As the educational institutions are the research sample, they were likely to have such statements about high-quality education, leading positions in their fields, and having the best possible scientific assets and research development. While the academic units mention contributions to national and regional development as mission statements, they also focus on essential matters for aviation, such as international collaboration and innovation.

To sum up, the content analysis of the mission statements of aviation education institutions in Türkiye reveals several critical implications for the stakeholders in the aviation education sector. These implications not only shed light on the current state of academic institutions but also provide valuable insights into the alignment and potential areas for improvement.

In conclusion, these implications and recommendations aim to guide academic institutions, policymakers, and industry stakeholders in enhancing aviation education's quality, relevance, and global impact in Türkiye. By addressing these areas, the aviation education sector can continue to play a pivotal role in shaping a highly skilled and forward-thinking workforce for the dynamic and evolving aviation industry.

5. Conclusion

This study aims to unravel the intricacies of educational policies within the aviation landscape by examining the core missions and visions of Turkish academic units offering bachelor's degrees in aviation. While this exploration provides a foundational understanding, a more comprehensive view could be achieved by incorporating the perspectives of industry stakeholders through their vision and mission statements.

From a mission standpoint, educational institutions play a crucial role in cultivating a proficient workforce for the aviation sector. The commitment to education and training resonates strongly, supported by scientific studies, global competitiveness, and interdisciplinary approaches. This forward-thinking orientation harmonizes academic objectives with the dynamic needs of aviation and space sciences.

The vision statements reflect a global perspective. These academic units aspire to achieve global recognition, leading positions in aviation education, and contribute to national and regional development. The emphasis on scientific excellence, innovation, and international collaboration demonstrates a commitment to nurturing visionary leaders and contributors to the ongoing evolution of the aviation industry.

Looking ahead, it is recommended to extend the analysis to include educational institutions from diverse countries. This exploration could uncover commonalities and differences, guiding Turkish educational institutions to refine and align their policies with international counterparts.

As Türkiye charts its course in the aviation education sector, these insights illuminate the path towards sustained excellence. The analysis aims to inform academic institutions, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. It also acts as a guiding compass for steering aviation education towards a future of innovation, collaboration, and commitment.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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